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Non-Regular Employment in the Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2020

They grew by 9.34% between 2004 and 2020

Istat calculates the value of irregular workers in the Italian regions. The variable is calculated as the percentage of employees who do not comply with current legislation on labour, tax and social security matters out of the total number of employees. The data refers to Italian regions and macro-regions between 2004 and 2020.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of non-regular employed in 2020. Calabria is in first place by value of non-regular employed in 2020 with a value of 20.9 units, followed by Campania with an amount of 17.9 units and by Sicily with a value of 17.3 units. In the middle of the table is Abruzzo where 13.6% of those employed are irregular, followed by Umbria with 12.4%, and Liguria with 11.4%. Friuli Venezia Giulia closes the ranking with 9.2% of irregular workers out of the total employed, followed by Trentino Alto Adige with 8.9 units and Veneto with 8.5 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in non-regular employed between 2004 and 2020. Basilicata is in first place by value of the percentage change in non-regular employed between 2004 and 2020 equal to an amount of 57.95% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 8.8 units up to a value of 13.9 units equal to a variation of 5.1 units. Molise follows with a variation equal to an amount of 55.00% equal to a variation from an amount of 10.00 units up to 15.55 units equal to an amount of 5.5 units. Piedmont follows with a variation of 50.77% equal to a variation from an amount of 6.54 units in 2004 up to a value of 9.8 units in 2020 equal to an amount of 3.3 units.

In the middle of the table are Umbria with a variation equal to an amount of 8.77% corresponding to a variation from 11.4 units in 2004 up to a value of 12.4 in 2020. Followed by Friuli Venezia Giulia with a variation equal to an amount of 8.24% corresponding to an amount of 8.5 units up to a value of 9.2 units equal to an amount of 0.7 units. Finally, Tuscany with a variation equal to 7.37% corresponding to a variation between 9.5 units in 2004 up to a value of 10.2 units in 2020 equal to an amount of 0.7 units.

Sicily closes the ranking with a value of -6.99% equal to a reduction from an amount of 18.6 units in 2004 to a value of 17.3 units in 2020 equal to an amount of -1.3 units. Lombardy follows with a variation of -12.96% equal to a variation from an amount of 10.8 units in 2004 up to a value of 9.4 units in 2020 equal to a variation of -1.4 units. Campania closes the ranking with a variation of -30.08% equal to a variation from an amount of 25.6 units in 2004 up to 17.9 units in 2020 corresponding to a variation of -7.7 units. Overall, the average value of irregular workers in the Italian regions between 2004 and 2020 grew from an amount of 11.6 units up to a value of 12.6 units, equal to a variation of 1.08 units corresponding to an amount of 9.34%.

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Non-regularly employed in the Italian Macro-Regions between 2004 and 2020. The value of non-regularly employed in the North grew from an amount of 8.90 units up to a value of 9.40 corresponding to a change of an amount of 0.50 units equal to a value of 5.62%. The value of non-regular employed people in the North-West grew by an amount equal to 3.19% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 9.40 units up to a value of 9.70 units equal to an amount of 0.30. The value of non-regular employed in the North-East between 2004 and 2020 grew from an amount of 8.10 units up to a value of 8.90 equal to a variation of 0.80 units equal to an amount of 9, 88%. The value of non-regular employed people in the Italian regions remained unchanged between 2004 and 2020 at an amount of 12.40 units corresponding to a variation of 0.0 units. The value of non-regular employed people in the South decreased from a value of 18.50 units in 2004 to an amount of 16.70 units in 2020, equal to a variation of -1.80 units corresponding to a variation of -9.73%. The value of non-regular employed people in Southern Italy decreased from an amount of 19.40 units in 2020 to a value of 16.80 units in 2020 corresponding to a variation of -2.60 units equal to an amount of -13, 40%. The value of non-regular employed people in the Islands grew from an amount of 16.50 units in 2004 up to a value of 16.60 units in 2020 or equal to a variation of 0.10 units corresponding to a variation of 0.61%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Three different clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Abruzzo, Lazio, Molise, Sardinia, Puglia, Basilicata, Umbria;
- Cluster 2: Emilia Romagna, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Trentino Alto Adige, Veneto, Valle d'Aosta, Piedmont, Marche, Lombardy, Tuscany, Liguria;
- Cluster 3: Calabria, Campania, Sicily.

From the point of view of the ordering of the clusters it is possible to identify the following structure: C3>C1>C2. Therefore we note that there is a contrast between the regions of the Centre-South which have high values of irregular workers and the regions of the Centre-North which instead have low values. However, we note that if on the one hand the average trend of cluster 3 tends to be decreasing in the observation period, i.e. between 2004 and 2020, on the other hand the average trend of cluster 2 and cluster 1 is increasing. It follows that a convergence of the regions of Cluster 3 towards the regions of Cluster 2 is very probable with the creation of homogeneity in the creation of a system

Conclusions. Non-regular employed people grew on average in the Italian regions between 2004 and 2020 by a value of 9.34%. There are only five regions in which there was a reduction in the value of non-regular workers between 2004 and 2020, namely: Veneto with -1.16%, Lazio with -5.3%, Sicily with -6.99%, Lombardy with -12.96% and Campania with -30.08%. The growth of non-regular workers in some regions of the North between 2004 and 2020 is very particular, i.e. Piedmont with +50.77%, Trentino Alto Adige equal to 27.14%, Emilia Romagna with +19.23%, and Friuli Venezia Giulia with +8.24%. In Italy in 2020 the value of non-regular employed people was equal to 12.00%. This is a worrying fact as it highlights a weakness in the Italian labor market in which new phenomena of job impoverishment co-exist. In fact, to the non-regular employed, we must add the over-educated employed and the low-paid employed. Adding these elements together we note that even if the value of the employment rate has grown, the quality of work, remuneration and professional qualification in the Italian regions show a decreasing trend, raising the question of the usefulness of work for the purposes of emancipating the lives of workers. What the data highlights is that the employment rate has grown in Italy, however Italians are no longer able to improve their economic and social condition through work due to the phenomena of irregular work, low-paid work and over-educated workers.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Calabria Campania Sicilia Molise Puglia Sardegna Lazio Basilicata Abruzzo Umbria Liguria
 Toscana Valle d'Aosta Marche Piemonte Lombardia Emilia-Romagna Friuli-Venezia Giulia
 Trentino-Alto Adige Veneto

- Basilicata ■ Molise ■ Piemonte ■ Valle d'Aosta ■ Liguria ■ Sardegna ■ Trentino-Alto Adige ■ Emilia-Romagna ■ Umbria
- Friuli-Venezia Giulia ■ Toscana ■ Calabria ■ Marche ■ Puglia ■ Abruzzo ■ Veneto ■ Lazio ■ Sicilia ■ Lombardia
- Campania

